
REPRESENTATION OF SOCIAL ACTORS IN THE CASE OF TEACHER BULLYING IN CENTRAL MALUKU BY DETIK.COM AND TRIBUN AMBON**Santuso Santuso**

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ABSTRACT

Mass media represents the image of individuals or groups in either a positive or negative light, depending on the media's perspective. This research aims to describe, interpret, and uncover the representation of social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku, including student and teacher perpetrators, bullied teachers, school principals, and local education authorities. This study employs critical qualitative descriptive research. The research data consist of diction, sentences, and metaphors representing social actors in the bullying case. Data sources are news articles from Detik.com and Tribun Ambon, with four articles selected from each published in August-September 2023. The data is analyzed using Norman Fairclough's critical discourse analysis theory. The results indicate that in textual analysis, Tribun Ambon tends to represent each social actor more positively compared to Detik.com. In the dimension of discursive practice, Detik.com relies on a single information source, resulting in unbalanced news reporting, while Tribun Ambon selects multiple sources, leading to more balanced reporting. In the socio-cultural practice dimension, it is evident that the reporting of bullying events is influenced by situational, institutional, and social contexts.

Keywords: Bullying; Critical Discourse Analysis; Norman Fairclough; Mass Media; Teacher.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of mass media, language plays a crucial role in conveying news and information to the public. However, beyond its informational function, not many people realize that language can also be used to shape worldviews, influence public opinions, and even construct reality itself (Sobur, 2006: 88). In the modern information era, mass media holds significant influence in shaping an individual's perception of the world. This is because mass media has the capacity to represent specific parties.

It is important to note that news delivered through mass media is not always neutral (Santuso, Wibisono, & Sukarno, 2023). The issue of neutrality in mass media reporting is a crucial subject in communication and journalism studies. The concept of neutrality creates space for an analytical approach known as critical discourse analysis (CDA). CDA is an approach that goes beyond analyzing words in a text; it critically analyzes language as a social practice to express ideologies and power relations in a social context (Wiratno, 2018: 375; Yasa, 2021: 90–91). It also aims to analyze any forms of social imbalance represented through language (Febriyanti & Suyudi, 2022). CDA examines the language used in news and analyzes how it reflects or shapes certain biases.

One event that can serve as evidence of media bias is the bullying incident involving a teacher named Maryam Latarissa, Vice Principal of SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah. Due to policies implemented by Maryam that contradicted prevailing rules, students eventually staged

a protest at their school. During the protest, some students engaged in bullying against Maryam Latarissa. This act was carried out by several students while being recorded by others. The 31-second video recording was later uploaded on social media, becoming viral and a topic of public discussion. Consequently, various mass media outlets reported on the incident.

Among these mass media outlets, there is one that focuses on reporting the incident from the perspective of the causes behind the students protest that led to the bullying of Maryam, such as Detik.com (Lamaau, 2023). On the other hand, there are also media outlets that concentrate on reporting the incident from the angle of Maryam's response and the school's reaction to the bullying case, one of which is Tribun Ambon (Mukadar, 2023). Therefore, the conclusion that can be drawn is that in the process of constructing reality, mass media is sometimes not neutral and may lean towards certain parties. Thus, the representations made by mass media also tend to have biases.

This article aims to reveal how mass media represents social actors related to the bullying case experienced by Maryam Latarissa. Hence, this article will provide a deeper understanding of the role of language in shaping social reality and how news consumers can develop critical skills in analyzing content presented by mass media. The article utilizes CDA based on Norman Fairclough's model.

Research on news in mass media using CDA as an analytical tool has been conducted by various parties, addressing political, criminal, social, religious, cultural, educational, literary, and other issues. This indicates that such research is intriguing and crucial as it can raise awareness and critical understanding of the hidden motives behind news production by mass media. In other words, CDA research can uncover meanings that are not immediately apparent in the media's reporting (Silaswati, 2019).

Based on the above description, the problem formulation in this article is divided into three parts: a) What linguistic features are used by Detik.com and Tribun Ambon in representing social actors in the case of bullying against Maryam Latarissa?; b) What discursive practices are employed by Detik.com and Tribun Ambon in representing social actors in the case of bullying against Maryam Latarissa?; and c) Why do Detik.com and Tribun Ambon differ in representing social actors in the case of bullying against Maryam Latarissa?

Relevant previous research has been conducted by various parties, including studies by Annisa & Baskoro (2023); Maghvira (2017); Simannungkalit & Kusumawati (2021); Tenriawali (2018); and Yanti, Fata, & Anwari (2021). Annisa & Baskoro (2023) investigated the representation of bullying cases against elementary school students in Tasikmalaya. Maghvira (2017) studied the representation of bullying cases carried out by senior cadets leading to the death of junior cadets at STIP Jakarta. Simannungkalit & Kusumawati (2021) explored the representation of violence by high school teachers in Bekasi against their students and cases of bullying by middle school students in Purworejo against their juniors. Tenriawali (2018) examined the representation of violence victims reported by makassar.tribunnews.com. Meanwhile, Yanti et al. (2021) investigated the representation of the assault on a junior high school girl in Pontianak by several high school students.

Overall, these five previous studies examined bullying and violence cases using CDA. The majority of these studies focused on the representation of bullying cases perpetrated by one student against another. From these studies, it is evident that each media outlet reporting bullying and violence cases tends to have its own tendencies, influenced by the background of the media and the parties involved. Based on the literature review conducted, it can be concluded that the upcoming research is innovative in terms of its research object. The reason being that there is no existing research on the representation of bullying cases involving a teacher, such as the case experienced by Maryam Latarissa.

2. THEORY

A. Representation Theory

According to Trianto (2013: 10), representation is the process of transforming abstract ideological concepts into concrete forms. Mulyana (2021: 56) states that in the context of mass media discourse, representation is related to the ways in which mass media presents social reality in textual forms. In addition, Gunalan, Handayani, & Yasa (2021) suggest that representation is a process of interpreting existing concepts in the mind using language. In other words, representation can be understood as the means of understanding, describing, and depicting an object, whether it's an individual, a group, or an idea. Rodin (2022: 204) explains that representation is a crucial concept with two main purposes. First, the study of representation aims to reveal whether someone, a group, or an idea is portrayed accurately or negatively. Second, this study of representation discusses the linguistic features used to present or describe a particular individual, group, or idea.

B. Critical Discourse Analysis Model by Norman Fairclough

Critical discourse analysis (CDA) is an approach that goes beyond merely analyzing the words in a text. It delves deeper into critically examining language as a social practice for expressing ideology and power relations in a social context (Wiratno, 2018: 375; Yasa, 2021: 90–91). It is also used to analyze all forms of social imbalances represented through language (Febriyanti & Suyudi, 2022). In other words, CDA is a method used to uncover and understand how meaning is constructed in language, including how ideology and power are reflected in discourse. CDA is a valuable linguistic study in raising awareness of power dynamics among news readers in mass media. Andriani (2019) also argue that language is a tool for exercising power to achieve the desired goals of the speaker or writer.

Norman Fairclough's model of CDA is an approach that connects micro-level text with macro-level societal contexts. Fairclough views discourse as inseparable from the broader social and cultural context, and thus, discourse analysis should encompass comprehensive analysis. Fairclough divides CDA into three dimensions: textual analysis, discourse practice, and sociocultural practice (Fairclough, 2010: 132).

The first dimension of Fairclough's CDA is text analysis. This first dimension is the descriptive phase. It involves analyzing various linguistic aspects such as vocabulary, grammar, syntax, and sentence coherence (Jorgensen & Philips, 2010: 129). Text analysis in this dimension also involves intertextuality, which means connecting the text with other texts. Intertextuality can be in the form of quotations, references, or content from other texts that influence the meaning within the analyzed text. The second dimension of Fairclough's CDA is discourse practice. This second dimension is the interpretative phase. Discourse practice affects how texts are formed. The emergence of a text is not solely based on individual desires and interests but involves organizations with diverse interests. In this dimension, the focus is on the interpretation of discourse, which involves interpreting the process of text production by the media and text consumption by the audience. The third dimension of Fairclough's CDA is sociocultural practice. This third dimension is the explanatory phase. In this dimension, analysis is based on the broader social context outside the media that impacts the discourse appearing in the media. This dimension refers to a wider context, including institutional, cultural, and political practices. It involves situational, institutional, and social contexts.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research falls within the realm of qualitative-critical research. Prasetyo & Sukarno (2022) assert that qualitative-critical research is a type of study that aims to describe, interpret, and criticize data based on how media constructs a certain reality. The research data consist of

diction, sentences, and metaphorical language styles representing social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku. Data sources for this study are two online media platforms, Detik.com and Tribun Ambon, with articles published in August-September 2023. The researcher selected four articles from each data source to represent the study.

Data collection involved the use of the observation and note-taking technique. Data were gathered by carefully, thoroughly, and critically reading written online news, marking sections of the text indicating the representation of the bullied teacher. The marked data were then selected and arranged according to the needs of the data analysis. In sorting the data, this study used the codes DE, TA, and P, along with numbers. DE stands for Detik.com, TA stands for Tribun Ambon, and P stands for paragraph. For example, the code DE1P1 means the first news from Detik.com in the first paragraph.

After classification and sorting, the data were analyzed using the theory of CDA in Fairclough's model, which is elaborated into three dimensions: textual analysis, discursive practice analysis, and socio-cultural practice analysis (Fairclough, 2010: 132). Once the data analysis phase was complete, the next step involved presenting the results using an informal method. The analyzed data were detailed in ordinary sentences, without the use of phonetic symbols and the like.

4. DISCUSSION

This research aims to describe, interpret, and explain the representation of social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku by Detik.com and Tribun Ambon. The analysis of research data is conducted within three dimensions: textual analysis, discourse practice, and sociocultural practice. The following details these three analyses.

4.1. Textual Analysis

The first dimension of Fairclough's CDA model is textual analysis. In this dimension, the analysis is focused on various linguistic aspects such as words, phrases, clauses, sentences, and metaphors. Textual analysis also involves intertextuality, connecting one text to another through quotations, references, or the content of other texts that influence the meaning in the analyzed text. Based on textual analysis, it is revealed that there are differences in the representation carried out by Detik.com and Tribun Ambon regarding social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku. The social actors in question include the students and teacher perpetrators of bullying, the teacher victim of bullying, the school principal, and the local education office. The following provides a detailed explanation.

A. Representation by Detik.com

Based on the analysis of four news sources from Detik.com, it is evident that Detik.com represents social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku through linguistic elements such as diction, sentences, and metaphors.

Representation Through Diction

The first form of representation of social actors by Detik.com is through the choice of words or diction. The first and second social actors represented by Detik.com are the students and teachers both involved in the act of bullying. They share a common reason for engaging in bullying, as indicated in the following data.

- (1) *Aksi para siswa tersebut diduga karena **tidak terima** kebijakan kepala sekolah (Kepsek) yang menunjuk Maryam sebagai Wakasek.* (The students actions are allegedly due to their **dissatisfaction** with the school principal's decision to appoint Maryam as the vice principal) [DE2P1]

- (2) *Kejadian itu ada dua (faktor), tetapi memiliki hubungan yang kalau kita lihat secara umum, yaitu **ketidakpuasan** beberapa guru dengan kepala sekolah.* (There are two factors in the incident, but they are related in a way that, if we look at it in general, is the **dissatisfaction** of some teachers with the school principal) [DE2P1]
- (3) *"... Tapi yang aneh itu adalah (aksi siswa) **tidak dilarang oleh guru**. Padahal ada beberapa guru yang berdiri di situ, itu kan kejadian di depan sekolah," katanya. ("... But what's strange is that the (students actions) were **not prohibited by the teachers**. Even though there were several teachers standing there, it happened in front of the school," he said) [DE4P2]*

In the first data above, Detik.com reports that students bullied a teacher because they were dissatisfied with the school principal's decision. The mentioned decision of the school principal is the appointment of Maryam Latarissa as the vice principal. The phrase "dissatisfaction" indicates a general rejection or disagreement with the school principal's decision. Students who are not satisfied with the school's policy may have views or opinions that strongly oppose the policy, possibly to the extent of completely rejecting it. This represents a strong opposition by the students against their school principal. However, Detik.com does not provide further explanation about the logical reasons why the students were unwilling to have the previous vice principal replaced by Maryam, leaving room for varied interpretations and negative assumptions about Maryam Latarissa, such as being deemed incompetent, untrustworthy, and so on.

Furthermore, in data 2, Detik.com reports that the bullying of Maryam is caused by the dissatisfaction of teachers with the school principal. This dissatisfaction includes aspects of policy, management, and institution administration by the school principal. Additionally, in data 3, it is reported that when the students engaged in bullying, some teachers were near the students but did not prohibit the action. Thus, it can be understood that the teachers supported the act of bullying.

The next social actors are the principal of SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah and its vice principal, Maryam Latarissa. Referring to data 1-3 above, the principal and vice principal are the targets of the viral incident. They are represented as follows.

- (4) *Husein mengatakan sebelumnya para guru mengirim surat ... Surat itu ditujukan ke kepala dinas berisi pernyataan sekelompok guru yang **tidak puas dengan keberadaan kepala sekolah**.* (Husein said previously the teachers sent a letter... The letter was addressed to the head of the education office containing a statement from a group of teachers **dissatisfied** with the presence of the school principal) [DE2P2]
- (5) *"Ada majelis kode etik kita yang bisa mengadakan sidang dan memberikan putusan terhadap **kode etik apa yang dilanggar** oleh kepala sekolah dan **manajemen apa yang menjadi kelemahan dia**," tambahnya. ("There is our code of ethics council that can hold a hearing and give a decision on **which ethical code has been violated** by the school principal and **what weaknesses exist in his management**," he added) [DE2P4]*
- (6) *Maryam yang sedang duduk di sepeda motornya langsung **berdiri** sambil **melihat** ulah para siswa yang mengambil kunci motornya.* (Maryam, who was sitting on her motorcycle, immediately **stood up** while **watching** the students taking her motorcycle key) [DE1P5] [DE2P6] [DE4P6]

In data 4-5 above, Detik.com uses the phrase "dissatisfied" indicating that teachers protested against the school principal because they were dissatisfied with his performance. Additionally, the phrases "which ethical code has been violated" and "what weaknesses exist in his management" suggest the negative aspects or shortcomings of the school principal. Thus, Detik.com represents the school principal as having made policies that violate the ethical code, leading teachers to protest against him. Furthermore, reporting from the school principal's perspective is entirely absent in Detik.com's coverage. Despite being an authoritative figure at SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah, Detik.com does not provide information about the principal, and his name is never mentioned. Moreover, Detik.com does not cover the school principal's efforts to summon the students involved in bullying and their parents to apologize to the bullying victim. Based on this, it can be understood that Detik.com only focuses on representing the weaknesses of the school principal, suggesting that he lacks the competence to hold the position.

On the other hand, data 4 above narrates the events during the bullying incident. At that time, Maryam was sitting on her motorcycle. Subsequently, the students took the key to her motorcycle. Aware of this, Maryam simply stood and observed her students actions. Therefore, Maryam is represented as a powerless party, unable to do anything in the face of the bullying. Additionally, Detik.com does not focus on reporting Maryam's reactions or responses after experiencing the bullying.

The next social actor is the local education office, represented by Detik.com through Secretary of the Department of Education and Culture of Maluku, Husein. Among the social actors mentioned above, Husein is the most dominant social actor, as Detik.com solely relies on statements from Husein for the representation of all social actors in the bullying case. Husein, representing the local education office, is portrayed by Detik.com as follows.

- (7) *Terus terang, kami dari dinas pendidikan sangat menyayangkan peristiwa itu.* (Frankly, we from the education office **regret** the incident) [DE1P2]
- (8) *Lebih lanjut, Husein mengatakan pihaknya telah memerintahkan kepala cabang Disdikbud di Malteng untuk mendalami peristiwa itu. Dia menegaskan akan memberikan sanksi tegas kepada pihak-pihak yang terlibat.* (Furthermore, Husein said his side **had ordered** the branch head of the Education and Culture Office in Maluku Tengah to investigate the incident. He stressed that **strict sanctions** would be imposed on those involved) [DE1P4]
- (9) *Husein menuturkan rekomendasi itu bersifat pembinaan sehingga guru yang dimutasi ke berbagai sekolah di Maluku Tengah tidak jauh dari keluarga.* (Husein said the recommendation is **aimed at coaching** so that teachers who are transferred to various schools in Central Maluku are **not far from their families**) [DE4P4]

In data 7, Husein is presented by Detik.com as a representative of the Department of Education and Culture of Maluku, expressing concern about the bullying incident involving Maryam. Additionally, in data 8, Husein is depicted as a figure with authority, responsiveness, and decisiveness. The phrase "had ordered" indicates that Husein has the authority to give orders to subordinates, and these orders have been executed. This suggests that the education office is portrayed as promptly and actively investigating the bullying case for a swift resolution. The phrase "strict sanctions" also indicates that Husein is portrayed as someone who does not tolerate bullying, and those responsible must face punishments to serve as a deterrent. Despite this, Husein is also portrayed as humane. This is evident in data 9, which explains that teachers involved in bullying Maryam will face sanctions aimed at guidance. The

sanction involves a job transfer, but it takes into consideration the home and family of the involved teacher. Husein does not want the teacher to be transferred to a place far from their family.

Representation Through Metaphor

Detik.com's next form of representation is realized through the use of metaphor. A metaphor involves the use of words or phrases not in their literal sense but as a figure of speech based on comparison. Detik.com employs metaphors specifically to represent the teachers involved in bullying Maryam. Here's an elaboration.

- (10) Menurut Husein, ada **dalang** di balik aksi para siswa SMA Negeri 15 terhadap Wakaseknya. (According to Husein, there are **puppet master** behind the actions of the students of SMA Negeri 15 against their Vice Principal) [DE1P3]
- (11) Lanjut Husain, dari hasil pemeriksaan ... terungkap bahwa ada sekelompok guru yang **mendesain** peristiwa itu. (Husain continued, from the examination results... it was revealed that there was a group of teachers who **designed** the incident) [DE4P3]

In data 10, it is reported that there is a party provoking the students, encouraging them to bully Maryam. This is evident in the use of the metaphor "puppet master." Literally, a puppet master refers to someone who manipulates puppets. However, in this context, the term "puppet master" is a metaphor meaning 'someone who orchestrates, plans, or leads a movement covertly'. The metaphor suggests that the act of bullying by the students was not purely their own initiative but controlled by someone else. Additionally, in data 11, it is stated that the bullying was well-planned by a group of teachers. This is conveyed through the metaphor "designed." Literally, "designed" refers to the activity of creating patterns for clothing, buildings, and other objects. However, in the sentence's context, "designed" is a metaphor meaning the activity of planning the pattern of bullying to ensure it runs smoothly.

Representation Through Sentences

Detik.com's next form of representation is realized through the use of passive sentences. Generally, mass media uses active sentences to report something. However, in specific cases, they use passive sentences. In the case of Maryam's bullying, passive sentences are used to represent Maryam as follows.

- (12) Wakasek SMAN 15 Maluku Tengah, Maryam Latarisa **di-bully** siswanya pada Senin (14/8). Maryam **diteriaki** hingga kunci motornya **diambil** siswa saat berada di parkir. ... Maryam yang mengenakan seragam ASN warna coklat serta helm kuning **dikerumuni** sejumlah siswa. Peristiwa itu terjadi di halaman parkir sekolah. (The Vice Principal of SMAN 15 Maluku Tengah, Maryam Latarisa, **was bullied** by her students on Monday, August 14. Maryam **was shouted at** until her motorcycle key **was taken** by a student while in the parking lot. ... Maryam, wearing a brown civil servant uniform and a yellow helmet, **was surrounded** by a number of students. The incident took place in the school's parking lot) [DE1P5] [DE2P6] [DE4P6]

In data 12, several times Detik.com constructs the bullying event by using passive sentences. This can be seen from passive-form verbs: "was bullied", "was shouted at", "was taken", and "was surrounded". The use of passive sentences makes the perpetrators of bullying the object of the sentence, while the victim of bullying becomes the subject of the sentence. Although in data 6 above, Maryam is reported as being helpless, she is portrayed as the subject in data 12. This makes Maryam a highlighted figure in the sentence, aiming to evoke sympathy

from the readers towards the victim of bullying. Additionally, these passive sentences also blur the students as the perpetrators of bullying. This might be because the students are underage and influenced by others in their actions.

Apart from this data, no other data was found that represents Maryam differently. Detik.com did not produce news that explains Maryam's condition after being bullied by her students. Detik.com also did not produce news that provides space for Maryam to clarify the events that happened to her. Similarly, Detik.com did not produce news explaining the school principal's order to the bullying perpetrators to apologize to Maryam. Based on this, it can be explained that Detik.com only represents Maryam as a helpless victim, aiming to garner public sympathy. As a teacher and vice principal, Maryam is not represented by Detik.com as a dignified person who deserves an apology for the bullying incident, and it is not explained how she felt after experiencing bullying.

B. Representation by Tribun Ambon

Based on the analysis of four news sources from Tribun Ambon, it is known that Tribun Ambon represents social actors in cases of teacher bullying in Central Maluku through linguistic elements such as diction, sentences, and metaphors as follows.

Representation Through Diction

The first form of social actor representation by Tribun Ambon is through the use of diction. The first and second social actors represented by Tribun Ambon are the students and teachers involved in the bullying actions. They are represented as follows.

- (13) *Aksi para siswa ini **buntut sejumlah kebijakan** yang diberlakukan sekolah.* (The actions of these students are the **result of several school policies**) [TA1P3]
- (14) ***Berikut poin tuntutan para siswa:** Pembuatan tata tertib tidak sesuai dengan mekanisme yang seharusnya disusun melalui rapat MPK. Kedua, ada salah satu poin dalam aturan yaitu dilarang demo. Ketiga, keterlambatan siswa dibiarkan, tidak dapat menyelesaikan persoalan ini. ... (Here are the points demanded by the students: The creation of regulations is not in accordance with the mechanism that should be arranged through the MPK meeting. Second, there is one point in the rules, namely, demonstrations are prohibited. Third, student lateness is ignored, unable to resolve this issue. ...)* [TA1P4]
- (15) *"Ada 35 orang guru, tapi ditanya ternyata ada guru yang tidak terlibat secara langsung tetapi namanya dan parafnya juga ada dalam aksi **mosi tidak percaya** terhadap kepala sekolah SMA 15," jelas Tomagola.* ("There are 35 teachers, but when asked, it turns out that there are teachers who are not directly involved but their names and signatures are also in the **vote of no confidence** against the headmaster of SMA 15," explained Tomagola) [TA4P3]
- (16) *Dikatakan, guru yang terlibat dalam **aksi demo** yang berujung aksi bullying terhadap seorang guru senior pada satuan pendidikan menengah atas itu berjumlah lebih 35 orang.* (It is said that the teachers involved in the **demonstration**, which led to the bullying of a senior teacher in the high school unit, amounted to more than 35 people) [TA4P2]

In the data 13, it is reported that dozens of students bullied Maryam. The cause is because they find several school policies chaotic. Then, in data 14, Tribun Ambon constructs the reality that there are nine policies made by the new headmaster and vice-headmaster, namely Maryam, which are considered chaotic. Due to these chaotic policies, students staged

a protest that ultimately led to bullying. This indicates that Tribun Ambon represents students as those who only want to voice their opinions and did not intend to bully from the beginning.

In data 15, it is explained that there are 35 teachers at SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah who are involved in the vote of no confidence against the headmaster. This depicts that the teachers no longer have trust or support for the headmaster and want the headmaster to be dismissed or replaced. A vote of no confidence is usually submitted when members of the organization (teachers) feel that their leader (headmaster) is ineffective, incompetent, or taking actions deemed detrimental to the school institution. In data 16, this action is described using the term "demo" which is an allegro form of the word demonstration. In this data, it can be understood that the teachers are protesting because they no longer have trust in the headmaster. However, Tribun Ambon does not tell the reason why the teachers do not trust the headmaster. This shows that Tribun Ambon wants to hide the weaknesses of the headmaster that led to protests by the teachers.

The next social actors are the headmaster of SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah and the vice-headmaster. These two individuals are represented by Tribun Ambon as follows.

- (17) *"Dan sebelum Konfrensi pers ini saya sudah **memberikan maaf** untuk mereka karena itu anak anak saya, **saya ikhlas,**" ungkap Maryam. ("And before this press conference, I have already **forgiven** them because they are my children, I **sincerely forgive,**" expressed Maryam) [TA3P2]*
- (18) *"Kejadian ini adalah merupakan **cobaan** karena kita sebagai **umat beragama.**" (This incident is a **trial** because we are believers) [TA3P3]*
- (19) ***Menjawab itu,** Kepala Sekolah, Amsuddi berjanji akan mengundang seluruh dewan guru dan para siswa untuk **mencari jalan keluar** dan meyelesaikan masalah tersebut. (**Responding to that,** the Headmaster, Amsuddi, promised to invite the entire board of teachers and the students to **find a way out** and resolve the issue) [TA2P4]*
- (20) *Sementara itu, Kepala Sekolah memastikan segera **memanggil orang tua siswa** untuk **menyelesaikan persoalan tersebut.** (Meanwhile, the Headmaster ensured to immediately **summon the parents of the students** to **settle the matter**) [TA3P4]*
- (21) *Dia berencana akan video dimana para siswa **meminta maaf** secara langsung kepada korban. (He plans to make a video where the students **apologize** directly to the victim) [TA3P5]*

In data 17, after experiencing bullying, Maryam is depicted as having forgiven the students who bullied her. Maryam considers them like her own children. She sincerely forgives them and does not harbor any resentment, anger, or disappointment toward her students. Additionally, in data 18, Maryam is represented as a religious and patient teacher. This is because she views the incident that happened to her as a trial that comes from God, and it needs to be faced with patience. Maryam associates this event with religious values. This can convey the message that she perceives the incident as a test from God, and this could be a way for her to alleviate the psychological impact of the event. Maryam formulates the event within a psychological and spiritual framework that adds meaning and value to her negative experience.

In data 19, the headmaster of SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah is represented as a responsible leader in resolving issues. After some alumni visited the school and urged him to take action, Tribun Ambon then portrays the role of the headmaster, Amsuddi. In the data above, Amsuddi is mentioned to be inviting all teachers and students to find a solution to the ongoing issues at their school. Furthermore, in data 20, Amsuddi is also described as

summoning the parents of the students. They are gathered with the aim of finding solutions to the problems at the school. One of the solutions is mentioned in data 21, where the students, accompanied by their parents, apologize to Maryam.

The last social actor represented by Tribun Ambon is the local branch leader of the education department. This can be understood from the following text.

- (22) *Kepala Cabang Dinas Pendidikan Provinsi Maluku di Masohi, Jabir Tomagola mengabarkan jika sejumlah guru yang terlibat dibalik aksi perundungan murid terhadap seorang guru di Masohi **terancam dimutasi**.* (The Head of the Provincial Education Office Branch in Maluku at Masohi, Jabir Tomagola, reported that a number of teachers involved in the bullying of a teacher by students in Masohi are **threatened with relocation**) [TA1P1]
- (23) *Ditegaskan, ada kemungkinan guru yang terlibat dimutasi di ke luar Maluku Tengah, namun di sini pihaknya juga **tidak mungkin memisahkan guru bersangkutan dengan keluarga mereka**.* (It is emphasized that there is a possibility that the involved teachers will be relocated outside of Central Maluku, but here his office **cannot separate the teachers from their families**) [TA4P4]
- (24) *"Siswa ini juga harus diberikan **sanksi**, tapi jangan yang berat, misalnya disuruh membuat tugas selama beberapa lama begitu agar ada efek jerah begitu," pinta Tomagola. "Kepala Sekolah harus panggil pers lalu bersama-sama dengan para guru dan siswa **meminta maaf** kepada guru bersangkutan dan kepada publik," tutup Tomagola. ("These students should also be given **sanctions**, but not severe ones, for example, they should be given assignments for some time so that there is an effect of remorse. The School Principal should call a press conference and together with the teachers and students **apologize** to the concerned teacher and to the public," Tomagola requested) [TA4P5]*

In data 22, Jabir Tomagola, as the Head of the Provincial Education Office Branch in Maluku at Masohi, is portrayed as someone firm and intolerant towards anyone involved in bullying within the school environment. This is evident from the choice of the phrase "threatened with relocation" which means teachers are threatened and the punishment for their involvement in bullying is relocation. Nevertheless, Tomagola is also represented as a humane figure. This can be seen in data 23, where it is explained that he also considers the fate of the teachers and their families if relocated too far. Therefore, he will relocate the teachers to areas near their homes.

Furthermore, in data 24, Tomagola is depicted as strict with the students who engaged in bullying against Maryam. Even though the bullying was not purely the initiative of the students themselves, essentially, the bullying was consciously carried out by the students. Therefore, the students are also at fault and need to be sanctioned for their actions. However, the sanctions imposed by Tomagola aim to create a deterrent effect so that they do not repeat the offense. Additionally, in the same data, Tomagola instructs the school principal to gather the teachers and students involved in the bullying to apologize to Maryam. This also indicates that Tomagola is portrayed as someone who cares about the feelings of the bullying victim.

Representation Through Metaphor

The next representation is manifested through the use of metaphors, portraying social actors such as students and teachers involved in bullying. This is evident in the following data.

- (25) *Menurutnya, para siswa tidak berniat melakukan itu, hanya saja diduga ada oknum lain yang **memanasi** mereka.* (According to him, the students did not

intend to do that, but there were suspicions that there were other elements **inciting** them) [TA3P3]

- (26) *Menurutnya, ada oknum yang memanasikan para siswa sehingga berbuat demikian.* (According to him, there were elements **inciting** the students to act in such a way) [TA2P2]

In the previous data (13-14), it was reported that students staged a protest after several school rules were implemented but contradicted the applicable regulations. Therefore, students demanded nine points to be changed or corrected. Hence, it can be understood that their initial intention was to demand changes to these nine points.

Subsequently, in data 25-26, students are portrayed as individuals who did not intend to engage in bullying against Maryam. In other words, the action was not purely the students' initiative but was influenced by other parties. This is evident from the use of the metaphor "inciting". Literally, the term "inciting" means an act of making something warm or hot. However, in this context, "inciting" is used metaphorically, meaning to incite or inflame the hearts of people to become angry, rebellious, or resist. Based on this, it can be understood that *Tribun Ambon* represents these students as not entirely culpable because their hearts and feelings were incited by others to engage in bullying.

The individuals who incited the students to carry out bullying were several teachers. As shown in data 15-16, 35 teachers initiated a vote of no confidence against the principal. To achieve their goal, which is the dismissal or replacement of the principal, they incited students to become angry with the school leadership, including the vice principal, Maryam Latarissa. However, the clear reasons behind the teachers' vote of no confidence are not elaborated on by *Tribun Ambon*. Based on this, it can be understood that *Tribun Ambon* focuses on representing the wrongdoing of the teachers without detailing their strong reasons for taking such actions.

Representation Through Sentences

The next representation is manifested through the use of passive sentences. Social actors represented include students and Maryam. This is evident in the following data.

- (27) *Dalam video berdurasi 31 detik itu, tampak kunci sepeda motor milik guru diambil salah seorang murid. Lantas ketika guru mencoba mengambil kunci sepeda motor, dia kemudian disoraki oleh belasan siswa. "Seng (Tidak) bisa pulang," sorak para siswa berulang kali. Kemudian kunci kendaraan baru diberikan oleh siswa setelah guru tersebut meminta berulang kali.* (In a 31-second video, it can be seen that the motorcycle key belonging to the teacher **was taken** by one of the students. Then, when the teacher tried to take back the motorcycle key, she **was jeered** by a dozen students. 'You cannot go home,' the students shouted repeatedly. Then, the vehicle key **was only given** by a student after the teacher requested it repeatedly) [TA2P5]

In data 27, *Tribun Ambon* constructs the bullying incident several times using passive sentences. This is evident from passive verbs: taken, jeered, and given. The use of passive sentences diminishes the importance of the bullying perpetrators, instead emphasizing the victim. *Tribun Ambon* might employ this approach because the bullying perpetrators are likely underage and influenced by others.

Furthermore, Maryam, as the victim of bullying, is portrayed as someone who still has the power to overcome the bullying. This is evident from the active voice in the sentence: "Then, when the teacher tried to take back the motorcycle key..." in the above data, indicating

that Maryam tried to prevent the bullying. Thus, Tribun Ambon does not represent Maryam as a powerless figure. Especially in data 17-21, Tribun Ambon represents Maryam as an honored individual, compelling the bullying perpetrators to apologize to her.

4.2. Discourse Practice Dimension

The second dimension in Fairclough's CDA model is the dimension of discourse practice, which focuses on analyzing the aspects of text production and reception. When applied to the representation of social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku, as reported by Detik.com and Tribun Ambon, several factors should be considered, including the background of these media outlets and their regulatory systems, along with the methods of news selection and presentation. Here is an analysis of this dimension related to the two online mass media.

Detik.com

Detik.com is an online news site in Indonesia that operates exclusively online and relies on advertising revenue. Although the Detik.com server has been active since May 30, 1998, the site was officially launched on July 9, 1998. This date is considered Detik.com's founding day, established by Budiono Darsono (former DeTik journalist), Yayan Sopyan (former DeTik journalist), Abdul Rahman (former Tempo journalist), and Didi Nugrahadi. The name "detik.com" was derived from the DeTik tabloid, existing since 1977 before being discontinued in 1994. On August 3, 2011, Detik.com became part of PT Trans Corporation, a subsidiary of CT Corp.

Initially focusing on political, economic, and information technology news coverage, Detik.com expanded its scope to include entertainment and sports as political situations stabilized and economic conditions improved. The concept of transforming Detik.com away from the characteristics of print media, divided into daily, weekly, or monthly patterns, emerged. Detik.com chose to offer instant breaking news to its readers, emphasizing in-depth and vivid descriptions. This approach made Detik.com one of the most popular digital information sites among internet users. However, a common criticism directed at Detik.com is the abundance of advertisements on its homepage.

In addition to national news, Detik.com covers regional news and has eight branch offices across various regions in Indonesia, including West Java, Central Java, East Java, Yogyakarta, North Sumatra, South Sumatra, Bali, and South Sulawesi. The coverage extends to nearby regional news corresponding to these branch offices. An example is the news of bullying against Maryam Latarissa, which occurred in Maluku and was covered by Detik.com's South Sulawesi branch. However, in reporting the bullying incident, Detik.com relied solely on one information source—the Secretary of the Department of Education and Culture of Maluku, Husein. This reflects an imbalance in Detik.com's reporting as it only presents a perspective from one information source. Possible reasons for Detik.com only interviewing one source could be the absence of Detik.com journalists in the Maluku region, laziness in seeking other sources, or pressure to quickly produce headline news.

Tribun Ambon

Tribun Ambon is a part of Tribunnews.com, operating as an online media platform in Indonesia under PT Tribun Digital Online. Established on March 22, 2010, and based in Jakarta, Tribunnews.com aims to be a driving force in Indonesia's digital transformation. Led by Dahlan Dahi as the Chief Operating Officer (CEO), Tribunnews provides information covering the entire archipelago, from Sabang to Merauke, through the Tribun Network.

The Tribun Network is strengthened by over 1,500 journalists representing local values from 38 provinces in Indonesia. It continues to expand its presence in both online and print media formats in various regions, supported by an online community called Tribunners spread across many provinces in Indonesia. Tribunnews.com emphasizes its motto, “*Mata Lokal Menjangkau Indonesia*” (Local Eyes Reach Indonesia), with a focus on reporting local news from a regional perspective.

Tribun Network excels in delivering news from various regions in Indonesia. As part of the Tribunnews family, Tribun Ambon was one of the first to report the bullying case involving Maryam Latarissa. In covering the incident, Tribun Ambon gathered information from various sources, including the perpetrators of the bullying, alumni of SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah, the school principal, the bullying victim (Maryam Latarissa), and the Branch Head of the Department of Education of Maluku Province, Jabir Tomagola. In terms of selecting sources, Tribun Ambon strives to present news in a balanced and comprehensive manner by involving diverse perspectives.

4.3. Sociocultural Practice Dimension

The third dimension of Fairclough's CDA model is the analysis of sociocultural practices. This analysis is based on the context that occurs outside the media but influences the media's discourse strategies. This context is divided into three types: situational, institutional, and social.

Situational Context

The situational context is a crucial aspect to consider in producing news. In the case of the bullying of a teacher in Central Maluku reported by Detik.com and Tribun Ambon, the situational aspect played a significant role. The incident began when Maryam Latarissa was in the school parking area on Monday, August 14, 2023. She was about to ride her motorcycle when suddenly several students surrounded Maryam. They quickly took Maryam's motorcycle key. Maryam asked the students to return the key, but they ignored her. They jeered at Maryam several times until she eventually shed tears.

The students also recorded the bullying incident. The 31-second recording was then uploaded to Facebook. Unexpectedly, the video became a topic of discussion among netizens on social media. The video was re-shared by others on various media platforms, eventually going viral on Tuesday, August 15, 2023 and becoming a serious issue. Due to its virality, Tribun Ambon covered the event as news on Wednesday, August 16, 2023. Subsequently, other media outlets also covered the incident. Detik.com reported on the event starting Friday, August 18, 2023. In the following days, both media outlets produced news that served as developments on the incident. Based on this, it can be understood that the production of this news was influenced by the occurrence of the bullying event, which tarnished the reputation of education. Therefore, it was deemed necessary to cover it so that more people would be aware of it, both regarding the causes and potential solutions.

Institutional Context

The institutional context considers the influence of institutions in the practice of discourse production. This includes both internal media institutions and external forces that impact news production. Advertisers, readers, inter-media competition, and media ownership are institutional elements influencing how news is produced.

Detik.com produced news on the bullying case involving Maryam Latarissa because the media offered a current and trending story for breaking news. Despite the incident occurring in Central Maluku, a remote area, Detik.com chose to cover it due to its virality on social media,

making it suitable for a headline story. Detik.com focused on a single source, the Secretary of the Department of Education and Culture of Maluku, aiming to generate fast and up-to-date news, aligning with their principle of presenting major news. Hence, it can be understood that their primary goal in news production is to generate revenue from advertisements, and not much more.

On the other hand, Tribun Ambon reported on the bullying incident involving Maryam because it occurred within their media coverage area, Maluku, reflecting alignment with their principle of "*Mata Lokal Menjangkau Indonesia*" (Local Eyes Reach Indonesia). As a result, readers may see this media outlet as consistent with this principle. Consequently, Tribun Ambon is likely to be the main reference for readers wanting to know about events in the region. Tribun Ambon also conducted interviews with various parties involved in the bullying incident, including the head of SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah and the Branch Head of the Department of Education of Maluku Province. By choosing authoritative sources, Tribun Ambon seeks to follow the development of the case until a resolution is reached. In this way, Tribun Ambon aims not only to generate advertising revenue but also to play a role as a media outlet engaging in social control. This means being a media entity that actively monitors and addresses societal issues.

Social Context

The social context also significantly influences the discourse that emerges in reporting. The evolution of media discourse is determined by this context. The social context focuses more on macro aspects such as the political, economic, cultural, and belief systems comprehensively within a society. The reporting on the bullying of a teacher in Central Maluku is inseparable from the culture, religion, and beliefs of the Indonesian society.

As a region adhering to Eastern cultural values, Indonesia places a strong emphasis on ethical principles and courtesy, especially in relation to a teacher. Eastern culture underscores the importance of cooperation, preserving the feelings of others, and upholding religious values. Indonesia, with a majority of its population being Muslim, including Maryam and most students at SMA Negeri 15 Maluku Tengah, demonstrates religious commitment through various signs, such as the wearing of the hijab by Maryam and the students involved in the bullying incident.

One of the teachings in religion is etiquette and courtesy. Teachers are respected as individuals who impart knowledge and dispel ignorance, holding a position worthy of respect. This concept is also found in the Quran in Surah Al-Mujadila, verse 11, which emphasizes that believers with knowledge hold a higher status. Therefore, the teaching profession is considered honorable in society. Consequently, bullying a teacher tarnishes the dignity of the teaching profession, making it necessary to cover the incident to investigate its causes and seek resolution.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the textual analysis outlined above, it can be concluded that Detik.com and Tribun Ambon represent social actors in the case of teacher bullying in Central Maluku in different ways. Detik.com's representations include (a) students opposing the school principal's policies, (b) some teachers supporting and controlling students in bullying actions, (c) portraying Maryam as a powerless figure deserving of sympathy, (d) depicting the school principal as incompetent, and (e) suggesting that the local education authorities have a firm and humane attitude. On the other hand, Tribun Ambon's representations include (a) students merely wanting to express their aspirations, initially having no intention to bully the teacher, (b) some teachers distrusting their school principal and inciting students to dislike the principal,

(c) portraying Maryam as an honored individual who deserves respect, is undeserving of bullying, is religious, and patient, (d) suggesting that the school principal still possesses competence, and (e) portraying the local education authorities as not only having a firm and humane attitude but also showing concern for the feelings of the bullying victim.

In terms of discursive practice analysis, it is evident that Detik.com covered the bullying incident because it went viral on social media. The media relied on breaking news and only one information source, resulting in unbalanced news reporting. On the other hand, Tribun Ambon covered the incident because the media focuses on reporting local news from a regional perspective. Tribun Ambon strives to present news in a balanced and comprehensive manner by involving multiple sources. In the socio-cultural practice dimension, it is known that the reporting of the bullying incident is influenced by three contexts: the situation, institutions, and social factors.

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